

Exploring regional mobility patterns based on statistical grids and dynamic mobile phone data

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Abstract. This study proposes a novel methodology for delineating employment areas, utilizing commuting patterns previously published by the Statistical Bureau of Finland. The proposed methodology involves the creation of origin-destination matrices and the implementation of clustering techniques, leveraging statistical and mobile phone tracking data as sources. The findings of this study demonstrate significant differences between the commuting zones, with mobile phone tracking-based networks exhibiting broader travel patterns in comparison to those derived from statistical data. Future research aims to integrate both datasets for improved commuting analysis with potential nationwide applications.

Submission Type. dataset, analysis, case study

BoK Concepts. Analytical methods, Geospatial data, Cartography and Visualization

Keywords. accessibility, commuting, mobility

1 Motivation

Until 2023, Statistics Finland defined and published employment areas for each municipality. According to Statistics Finland's definition, the employment area consisted of the central municipality and the connected municipalities with a commuting share of at least 10% (Tilastokeskus, 2025). Due to the changing spatial structure of employment and the merging of municipalities, the method used has become imprecise (Kotavaara et al., 2020). The aim of this research is to produce new and more accurate indicators based on accurate population, workplace and commuting grid cell data and mobile phone tracking data.

2 Study setting

Northern Ostrobothnia is one of Finland's 19 regions and the most populous region in Northern Finland, including urban cores and rural peripheries (Fig 1.) (Söderström et al., 2015). It has a population of about 420,000 in 30 municipalities, with half of the population living in Oulu, the region's largest city. It covers an area of around 37,000 square kilometres with low population density of 11 people per square kilometre (Pohjois-Pohjamaan Liitto, 2025).

Figure 1: Regions of Finland, with urban-rural classification. North Ostrobothnia highlighted.

Population trends in rural areas are challenging, while large urban areas are experiencing population

growth. Understanding commuting patterns is therefore critical to future service design and workforce availability.

3 Data and analysis

The analytics and new indicators for commuting patterns were produced using two main data sources: 1) statistical grid cell data and 2) mobile phone tracking data.

3.1 Statistical grid cell data

Register-based statistical grid cell data on population, workplace and commuting data was obtained from Finland's Monitoring System of Spatial Structure and Urban Form (YKR) provided by the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and Statistics Finland (Finnish Environment Institute, 2025). In the project, an origin-destination matrix has been created utilizing population and employment statistics from 2021. In the matrix, each employed person is represented by one journey between their place of residence and their place of work. The location of the place of work may coincide with the location of the place of residence. The data does not consider teleworking or mobility activity. The data on the residence-workplace grid pair were also aggregated to the 5×5 km² grid level for a more detailed spatial structure of employment.

3.2 Mobile phone tracking data

Mobile phone tracking data provided by Telia Crowd Insights is a dataset based on recorded network events between mobile phones and mobile cell towers within the cellular network of Telia Oyj, which is one of the largest mobile network operators in Finland. The network events are anonymised, aggregated and extrapolated, to create an origin-destination matrix (Telia Finland Oyj, 2024). The Telia Crowd Insights data is produced in a grid scaled between 500×500 m² and 32×32 km², with the core data at 1×1 km²-8×8 km² grid level. The analysis encompasses all recorded journeys taken between 19th January and 19th February 2023, and 2 a.m. to 12 a.m. The period was chosen due to the low number of holidays or events linked to tourism.

3.3 Aggregation and clustering

The analysis of mobility patterns derived from the YKR home-work grid cell pairs and the mobile phone tracking data can be further delineated by establishing commuting zones. A novel clustering method has been developed for the analysis of commuting areas, incorporating the distance

between origin and destination cells and the strength of commuting flows (Eq. 1):

$$C_{comm} = \frac{T_{trip}}{d_{O-D}} \quad (1)$$

where T is the number of trips and d is the distance between the midpoint of the origin and destination grid cells. By utilising the derived commuting coefficient (C_{comm}), all commuting flows within a selected municipality can be systematically ranked. To identify the most significant commuting zones, a threshold is applied to limit the proportion of flows considered. The upper quintile of travel flows to each municipality in the region was considered, with the higher 50th, 60th, 70th and 80th percentiles considered. Once the selection threshold percentage has been determined (for example, 70%), all commuting trips directed towards the selected municipality are aggregated, starting with the highest flow values. This process is repeated until the cumulative sum of commuting trips reaches 70% of the total commuting volume. Once this selection has been made, a concave polygon is generated from the resulting matrix to delineate the commuting area.

3.4 Data and software availability

The statistical data is available after registration through SYKE's YKR data distribution service. The compiled datasets cannot be redistributed due to licensing restrictions, but licence to the data can be requested with a separate application and is a subject to a fee. The authors do not have permission to share the mobility data provided by Telia Crowd Insights. The analyses were conducted in QGIS 3.36.3 and Python 3.12 using Pandas and NumPy.

4. Results, discussion

A simultaneous spatial analysis of the commuting zones was conducted, utilising a zone stacking and zone summing analysis. This analysis visualised the commuting flows of each municipality, employing a 70% cutoff threshold in the zone creation process for

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